

AGRICULTURE IN TELANGANA: FROM PLIGHT TO PRIDE

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Introduction	01
Gross Value added from Agriculture	02
Budget of Agriculture	05
Production of Crops	07
- Foodgrains - Paddy	07
- Coarse Cereals - Maize	09
- Non-Food Grains	10
Cotton	10
Oil Palm	10
- Horticulture	11
Poultry Products	13
Government Initiatives	13
- Agriculture Inputs	14
Power	15
Irrigation	15
Seeds & Fertilisers	17
Mechanisation - Lesser Drudgery	19
- Rythu Bandhu - Financial Aid for Farmers	20
- Rythu Bima - Insurance for Farmers	22
- Rythu Vedika - Agriculture Extension	23
- Structural Reforms	23
Crop Diversification	23
Palm Oil Cultivation	24
Organic Farming	24

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- Agriculture Value Chain	25
Procurement	25
Milling and Warehouse Management	26
Processing	27
e-NAM	28
- Efforts of the Government in Strengthening Agriculture Statistics	28
- Allied Sectors - Animal Husbandry	29
Sheep Rearing and Development Programme (SRDP)	30
- Allied Sectors - Dairy	31
- Allied Sectors - Fodder Production and Development	31
- Allied Sectors - Poultry	32
- Allied Sectors - Aquaculture	32
Future Challenges	33
- Overproduction of Paddy and Cotton	33
- Crop Diversification	34
- Extreme Weather Conditions and Climate Change	35
- Cultivation of Palm Oil	36
- Expanding the Nutritious Food Basket	37
Conclusion	38
References	40

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INTRODUCTION

In less than ten years, the Telangana agriculture sector has considerably improved. The barren land of Telangana has turned green. The growth of gross value added at constant prices from agriculture from 2015-16 to 2021-22 is 7.4 per cent in contrast to the Indian growth rate of 4 per cent (Sri Harish, 2023). Additionally, the area under cultivation has risen from 131.33 lakh acres in 2014-15 to 215.37 lakh acres in 2021-22 (Sri Harish, 2023).

K. Chandrashekar Rao, the Chief Minister of the new state of Telangana had said in 2015 -

"I firmly believe that growth, and even legitimacy, has no meaning if the deprived sections of society are left behind. We fully share the concerns that inclusive growth should not only ensure a broad-based flow of benefits and economic opportunities, but also encompass empowerment and participation. The initiatives taken by the Government since the formation of the State in June this year have entirely been guided by these compelling imperatives" (Government of Telangana Planning Department, 2015).

The agriculture sector was one of the various focus areas in achieving their vision for the state. Almost 55.49 per cent of the state population depended on agriculture and allied activities (Government of Telangana Planning Department, 2015). Therefore, it was a necessity that farming and allied activities became a viable occupation to address poverty concerns. In the Telangana region, in 1968, 14 per cent of the total geographical area was fallow land (land which is cultivable land but not cultivated during the reported year) and in 2011 it increased to 23 per cent (Reddy et al., 2014). The high percentage of fallow land reflects the

neglect of the agriculture sector and low investments in land development for five decades (Reddy et al., 2014). The sector also faced many challenges, from water shortage, declining land productivity, unremunerative prices, high cost of cultivation and climate change (Government of Telangana Planning Department, 2015). So, various initiatives like farm loan waiver, Mission Kakatiya, and encouraging farm mechanisation to reduce the cost of cultivation were initiated. The massive growth and improvement raise the question of what has been done to reach this stage. The following sections will trace the trends related to agriculture indicators, various government initiatives and schemes that have assisted in reaching the state of agriculture it is today, and finally, the future challenges and the conclusion.

GROSS VALUE ADDED FROM AGRICULTURE

The Gross Value Added from Agriculture at constant prices in 2021-22 was Rs. 43,33,325 lakhs. The contribution of agriculture to the gross value added has grown by 46.6 per cent since 2014-15 (Figure 1). The average annual growth rate of the primary sector from 2015-16 to 2020-21 was 15.8 per cent and has been above the Indian average (8.5 per cent) and the highest among the South Indian States (Table 1 and Figure 2).

Figure 1 - Gross Value added by Agriculture from 2014-15 to 2021-22

Source: RBI Handbook of Statistics

Table 1: Annual Growth Rate (%) of the Primary Sector

State	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	Annual Average
Telangana	2.2	17.1	14.7	18.6	25.6	16.5	15.8
Andhra Pradesh	18	21	22.4	6.5	11.2	8.6	14.6
Karnataka	0.9	6.2	26.4	2.2	15.6	8.8	10
Tamil Nadu	3.8	3.8	18	7.9	12.5	10.1	9.4
Kerala	-2	9.3	8.9	-0.7	-1.6	NA	2.8
India	5	12.8	11.3	7.2	10.5	4.2	8.5

Source: Directorate of Economics and Statistics (Government of Telangana), 2021

The contribution of the primary sector to the Gross State Value Added (GSVA) at current prices in 2014-15 was 19.5 per cent, the secondary sector was 19.2 per cent, and the tertiary sector contributed the majority share of 61.3 per cent. In 2020-21, the contribution of the primary sector increased by 4.6 per cent to 24.1 per cent. The secondary and tertiary sectors have seen a fall in the contribution by 2.7 per cent and 1.9 per cent, respectively (Figure 3).

Figure 2 - Annual Growth Rate (%) of the Primary Sector

Source: *Telangana Journey from 2014-15 to 2020-21 (PE)*

Figure 3 - Sector Contributions (%) to GSVA

At current prices

Source: *Telangana Journey from 2014-15 to 2020-21 (PE)*

Within the agriculture sector, the contribution of Livestock to GSVA at current prices has seen an increase of 12.65 per cent from 2014-15 to 2020-21. And crops have seen a decline of 11 per cent during the same period (figure 4).

Figure 4 - Contribution of Sub Sectors to Agriculture GSVA

At current prices

Source: *Directorate of Economics and Statistics*

BUDGET OF AGRICULTURE

The Telangana government has made significant budget allocations towards agriculture and allied sectors over the years. Ten years before the formation of the State, Rs. 7,994 crores was spent on the agriculture sector. Whereas, post-formation of the state, the Government has spent a cumulative sum of Rs. 1,91,612 crore till January 2023 on the agriculture sector, which is twenty times more than what was spent in the ten years before 2014 (Sri Harish, 2023).

In 2023-24, Rs. 29,164 crores has been allocated towards agriculture and allied activities. The budget allocation more than tripled in 2018-19 from 2017-18 (PRS Legislative Research, 2023). The portion of the total expenditure allocated to agriculture and allied activities from 2018-19 to 2022-23 has been, on average, 13.8 per cent. Whereas, on average, in most other states, the allocation has been 6.5 per cent (PRS Legislative Research, 2023).¹

Telangana is the only State in India which has provided investment support of Rs. 65,000 crore to 65 lakh farmers under the Rythu Bandhu Scheme (Sri Harish, 2023). In the 2023-24 budget, a total of Rs. 11,704 crores was allocated for the investment support scheme for the farmers (PRS Legislative Research, 2023).

Over the years, the Government has also focused on debt relief for the farmers. Since the formation of the state, the Government has waived loans of 44.44 lakh farmers in two rounds (Sri Harish, 2022). From 2020-21 to 2022-23, the Government has allocated Rs. 13,753 crores for loan waivers and debt relief for farmers.

1 PRS Budget Analysis of Telangana from 2016-17 to 2023-24

Table 2: Telangana Budget Allocations for Agriculture and Allied Activities and Irrigation

Years	Agriculture and Allied Activities	Irrigation*
2016-17	6,611.00	24,132.00
2017-18	5,852.00	22,668.00
2018-19	17,252.00	24,969.00
2019-20	21,680.00	6,286.00
2020-21	25,305.00	4,704.00
2021-22	26,822.00	7,979.00
2022-23	27,228.00	10,946.00
2023-24	29,164.00	11,169.00

Source: Author Compilation (PRS Legislative Research, 2016-17 to 2023-24)

* From 2019-20, the budget allocation is for Irrigation and Flood Control

Ensuring water availability for irrigation has played an integral role in reaching this feat of progress in the agriculture sector. The Government of Telangana allocated considerable budgets in the early years of the state formation to invest in irrigation projects like the revival of tanks, Palamuru lift irrigation project, the Kaleshwaram project etc. From 2016-17 to 2018-19, the budget allocation for irrigation was above 20,000 crores (Table 2). After which there was a dip and is again on the increasing trend.

From the budget allocation for irrigation and agriculture and allied activities, it is visible that the Government of Telangana is keen on improving the agriculture sector. However, a point of concern is whether other essential areas of development are being sidelined in the midst of improving the agriculture sector. For instance, budget allocations for education, health, and rural development since 2018-2019 have consistently been much below the average allocations of most other Indian states (Table 3). For 2023-24, the allocation of total expenditure towards education is 7.6 per cent, whereas the average of other states in 2022-23 was 14.8 per cent (PRS Legislative Research, 2023). Similarly,

5 per cent of total expenditure was allocated for health, whereas other states, on average, have allocated 6.3 per cent of total expenditure (PRS Legislative Research, 2023).

Table 3: Allocation of total expenditure towards Education and Health by Telangana and the average of other states.

Budget Areas	Years	Telangana	Other States*
Education	2019-20	7.50%	15.90%
	2020-21	7.40%	15.90%
	2021-22	6.80%	15.80%
	2022-23	7.30%	15.20%
	2023-24	7.60%	14.80%
Health	2019-20	4%	4.50%
	2020-21	3.50%	5.30%
	2021-22	3%	5.50%
	2022-23	5%	6%
	2023-24	5%	6.30%

Source: Author Compilation (PRS Legislative Research, 2019-20 to 2023-24)

* Average of other states is calculated using the previous year's Budget Estimates

PRODUCTION OF CROPS

Foodgrains - Paddy

The major crops grown in Telangana are Paddy, Cotton, and Maize, constituting 80 per cent of the total produce (Government of Telangana, 2023). In 2020-21, the area under production of foodgrains was 3.38 million hectares and contributed to 3.34 per cent of total Indian production (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare et al., 2022).

Telangana has observed a massive 79 per cent increase in the production of food grains from 2014-15 to 2020-21 (Figure 5). Most of the increase is because of the increase in paddy production. In 2020-21, 12,745.6 thousand tonnes of foodgrains were produced, and paddy contributed 10,217.1 thousand tonnes. The area under cultivation for

paddy in 2020-21 was 2.31 million hectares, contributed 6.3 per cent of total Indian production (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare et al., 2022). Telangana was India's 6th largest producer of paddy in 2020-21, and the largest was West Bengal, followed by Uttar Pradesh (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare et al., 2022). Paddy production in Telangana has increased by 130 per cent from 4440.8 thousand tonnes in 2014-15 to 10,217.1 thousand tonnes in 2020-21.

Since the formation of the state, the paddy production in Andhra Pradesh production has been higher than in Telangana. However, In 2020-21, Telangana surpassed the paddy production of Andhra Pradesh by 2334.2 thousand tonnes (Figure 6). The state is now being referred to as 'Annapura' for the Country (Sri Harish, 2023). The yield of paddy in Telangana is 3327 kg/ hectare, which is higher than the Indian average of 2713 kg/hectare.

Figure 5 - Production of Food grains in Telangana from 2014-15 to 2020-21

In Thousand Tonnes

Source: RBI Handbook of Statistics

Figure 6 - Production of Paddy in Telangana and Andhra Pradesh

In Thousand Tonnes

Source: RBI Handbook of Statistics

Coarse Cereals - Maize

The production of coarse cereals has decreased by 20 per cent from 2404 thousand tonnes in 2014-15 to 1922.9 thousand tonnes in 2020-21 (Table 4). In 2020-21, the area under cultivation for coarse cereals was 0.37 million hectares and contributed 3.81 per cent to total Indian production (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare et al., 2022). The largest producer of coarse cereal in 2020-21 was Rajasthan which contributed 16.30 per cent to total Indian production (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare et al., 2022).

Within coarse cereals, the production of maize was on an increasing trend from 2015-16 till 2019-20. In 2015-16 the maize production was 1.75 million tonnes, which increased to 3 million tonnes in 2019-20. However, the production fell to 1.75 million tonnes in 2020-21 (Table 4). The contribution of maize production in Telangana to all India production fell from 10.43 per cent in 2019-20 to 5.55 per cent in 2020-21 (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare et al., 2022).

Table 4: Production of different crops in Telangana (in thousand tonnes)

Years	Foodgrains	Paddy	Coarse Cereals	Maize	Cotton
2014-15	7,114.80	4,440.80	2,404.00		3,800.00
2015-16	5,129.00	3,047.00	1,834.00	1,751.00	3,661.00
2016-17	8,484.60	5,173.40	2,768.20	2,882.00	3,444.00
2017-18	9,421.10	6,262.20	2,639.30	2,752.00	5,195.00
2018-19	9,275.20	6,670.00	2,155.70	2,083.00	3,847.00
2019-20	11,125.00	7,427.80	3,138.90	3,000.00	6,833.00
2020-21	12,745.60	10,217.10	1,922.90	1,750.00	5,797.90

Source²: Author Compilation

Non-Food Grains

Cotton: Among the non-food grains, cotton is a significant crop . Cotton production has increased by 52.5 per cent from 3,800 thousand tonnes in 2014-15 to 5,707.9 thousand tonnes in 2020-21 (Table 4). In 2020-21, Telangana contributed 16.94 per cent to the total Indian production and was the third largest producer after Maharashtra (27.1 per cent) and Gujarat (25.55 per cent) (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare et al., 2022).

Oil Palm: The Government is focusing on pushing the farmers towards cultivating oil palm in Telangana as water availability for irrigation has made it a viable crop for growing. Additionally, it is estimated that the farmers will get a net income of Rs.1,50,000 per annum per acre by cultivating oil palm (Sri Harish, 2023).In the 2023-24 budget, Rs.1,000 crore was allocated for oil palm cultivation. The crude oil palm production has increased more than four times from 2013-14 to 2019-20 (Table 5). The contribution to total India production has steadily

2 (Reserve Bank of India, 2022), (Government of Telangana, 2023), (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare et al., 2022)

increased from 5.18 per cent in 2013-14 to 14.93 per cent in 2019-20. The state is also the second largest producer of Oil Palm after Andhra Pradesh (Adititandon, 2022).

Table 5: Crude Oil Palm Production in Telangana (in tonnes)

Years	Telangana
2013-14	9,373.00
2014-15	10,012.00
2015-16	12,499.00
2016-17	8,947.00
2017-18	27,275.00
2018 19	37,205.00
2019-20	38,050.00
2020-21*	26,690.00

Source: Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare et al., 2022

* Provisional Estimates

However, there are concerns about the push towards cultivating oil palms as it is a water-intensive crop requiring 200 to 300 litres of water per day. Although it is seen that palm oil cultivation is being done on agricultural land and not in water-deficient districts of the state. Agriculture and Water experts have other opinions on how sustainable the cultivation is in an arid region like Telangana (Adititandon, 2022).

Horticulture

In 2020-21, the total area under cultivation for horticulture crops was 404.02 thousand hectares. Among different categories, fruits were cultivated on 171.74 thousand hectares, spices on 139.53 thousand hectares and vegetables on 88.34 thousand hectares (Table 7). The majority of the total production of 5238.89 thousand tonnes comes from fruits and vegetables.

The production of vegetables and fruits over the years has declined. The production of vegetables has declined by 46 per cent from 3,005

thousand tonnes in 2014-15 to 1,621 thousand tonnes in 2021-22 (Table 6)³. Similarly, even for fruits, production has declined by 57 per cent from 5,287 thousand tonnes in 2014-15 to 2,271.80 thousand tonnes in 2021-22 (Table 6).

Table 6: Production of Vegetables and Fruits in Telangana (thousand tonnes)

Category	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022*
Vegetables	3,005.30	3,195.40	1,647.00	2,753.80	2,574.30	2,274.50	2,150.20	1,621.60
Fruits	5,287.70	4,319.90	1,200.30	1,939.40	2,012.80	2,537.30	2,389.20	2,271.80

Source: RBI Handbook of Statistics

* 2nd Advance Estimates

Table 7: Production and Area under cultivation for different horticulture crops in 2020-21

Horticulture	Area (thousand hectares)	Production (thousand tonnes)*
Fruits	171.74	2389.57
Vegetables	88.34	1943.53
Plantation	0.79	5.99
Aromatics & Medicinal Flowers	0.31	5.65
Flowers (Loose)	3.31	47.99
Spices	139.53	845.31
Honey		0.85
Total	404.02	5238.89

Source: Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare et al., 2022

* 3rd Advance Estimates

- 3 Discrepancy in figures of production of vegetables in 2020-21 in Table 6 and Table 7 can be attributed to the different stages of estimates.

Poultry Products: The production of all poultry products has increased from 2014-15, except for wool. In 2020-21, Telangana was the 5th largest producer of meat. In 2020-21, it contributed to 10.45 per cent of the total meat production in India. In 2020-21, Telangana contributed 13 per cent of the total production in India and was the 3rd largest producer of eggs in India.

Table 8: Production of Milk, Fish, Wool, Egg, and Meat in Telangana

Products	Milk	Fish	Wool	Egg	Meat
2014-15	4,207.00	268.00	4,423.00	106,185.00	505.00
2015-16	4,442.00	237.00	4,562.00	112,058.00	542.00
2016-17	4,681.00	199.00	4,658.00	118,186.00	591.00
2017-18	4,965.00	270.00	4,506.00	126,700.00	645.00
2018-19	5,416.00	328.00	4,264.00	136,868.00	754.00
2019-20	5,590.00	300.00	3,960.00	148,055.00	848.00
2020-21	5,765.00	-	3,366.00	158,470.00	920.00

Source: Reserve Bank of India, 2022

The above data shows that the agriculture sector has grown in terms of contribution towards gross value added and production, especially in paddy and cotton. The following section will examine the various government initiatives attributed to the improvement in this short period.

GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES

Government policies at the national, state and local levels significantly influence every step of the agricultural value chain, from farmland to market. These policies can impact what crops farmers grow, where farms are located, transportation and processing of products, commodity trading, and the prices farmers receive. Therefore, it is crucial for government policies to strike a balance between the costs and benefits to farmers, consumers, the environment, government budgets, and competing interests to sustain and develop the agricultural sector.

Farmers' income primarily depends on crop yields and access to markets, which are determined by various factors such as water, power, fertilisers, seeds, labour, and mechanisation. Recognising the importance of the agricultural sector, the Telangana government has prioritised its growth and farmers' welfare through flagship initiatives. Some are improving irrigation through projects like Kaleshwaram Project and Mission Kakatiya, providing free 24x7 power to farmers, providing investment support through Rythu Bandhu, and offering life insurance under Rythu Bima.

The Government's idea in Telangana has been that 'everything can wait but not agriculture', emphasising the need for farmers to have timely access to funds for investment and credit facilities. Streamlining the availability of farm inputs such as seeds and fertilisers and providing timely extension services for improved yields are critical priorities. In response to increased agricultural production in the state over the years, the Government has implemented post-harvest management practices, including additional storage facilities and market linkages.

Recently, structural reforms such as promoting crop diversification through oil palm cultivation and adopting technology-enabled approaches to improve animal husbandry services have been initiated to address the challenge of surplus production.

To transform agriculture into a sustainable and profitable industry, the Telangana government has introduced several initiatives that have yielded positive results. In the following sections, we will delve into the key policies and initiatives implemented by the Telangana government to enhance the agricultural sector in the state.

Agriculture Inputs

Access to modern agricultural inputs is the foundation of any agricultural revolution. These inputs include improved seeds, fertilisers, crop protection chemicals, machinery, irrigation, and knowledge. Seeds are crucial for successful crop production and farm productivity.

Fertilisers provide essential nutrients to the soil for growth. Irrigation enables off-season farming, multiple harvests per year, and cultivates additional land. Crop protection chemicals control weeds, harmful insects, and plant diseases. Technical knowledge and machinery will enhance labour effectiveness and farm productivity.

The Government of Telangana recognises the importance of the timely and adequate availability of agricultural inputs and has implemented various initiatives to enhance crop productivity. They closely monitor and track the supply of seeds, fertilisers, and pesticides to farmers in the state. To improve irrigation facilities, the Government has implemented initiatives such as providing 24x7 free power for agriculture, making Telangana the only state in the Country with an uninterrupted power supply for agriculture at no cost.

Power: As per the Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook 2023, since January 1, 2018, the Telangana government has provided 24-hour free and quality power supply to agricultural consumers in the state. Around 40% of the total power supply in the state is allocated to agriculture. Since the formation of Telangana, 6.6 lakh new agricultural connections have been released, bringing the total number of agricultural connections to 26.22 lakhs. The Government has incurred an amount of Rs. 49,314 crores towards subsidies in terms of free power supply to farmers in the state since 2014-15. Presently, power consumption has increased to 3,500 MW, compared to 1,500 MW before the formation of the state. Telangana consumes the highest percentage (41.25%) of electricity for agricultural purposes at the all-India level, accounting for 24077 GWh out of the total energy sold of 58,365 GWh in 2018-19, as per Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023. Additionally, Telangana state also has the third largest power utility in the Country with an installed capacity of 4365.30 MW (EPTRI, n.d.).

Irrigation: Since 2014-15 to 2022-23, the Government has incurred an amount of Rs. 1,60,979 crores on irrigation projects. As a result, the

gross irrigated area (GIA) has significantly increased by 117% from 62.48 lakh acres in 2014-15 to 135 lakh acres in 2021-22, and additional new irrigation potential of 74.32 lakh acres has been created (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Table 9: Irrigation Initiatives.

Irrigation Initiatives	Achievements
Construction of Projects	<p>Major Projects commissioned-Kaleshwaram project (18.25 Lakh acres), Sita Rama Lift Irrigation Scheme (3.87 Lakh acres), J. Chokka Rao Devadula Lift Irrigation Scheme (5.58 Lakh acres), Rajeev Bhima Lift Irrigation Scheme (2.03 Lakh acres), Mahatma Gandhi Kalwakurthy lift irrigation scheme (4.24 Lakh acres), Jawahar Nettareddy Lift Irrigation Scheme (2.00 Lakh acres).</p> <p>Palamuru Rangareddy Lift Irrigation Scheme (PRLIS) (12.30 Lakh acres) and Devadula Lift Irrigation Scheme (DLIS) (3.61 Lakh acres) are in progress.</p>
Restoration of MI Tanks	27,472 Tanks restored with an expenditure of Rs.5,349 Cr, stabilising an ayacut of 15.05 Lakh acres. 8.93 TMC of storage capacity is restored
Construction of Check Dams	1,200 Check dams sanctioned for Rs. 3,850.00 Crs. In Phase-I, 638 check dams are in progress, and the remaining 562 are to be taken up under phase-II
IP Utilisation	IP utilised has increased to 97.57 Lakh acres during 2021-22, and our state became a major Paddy production state and the second largest in Paddy Procurement by FCI.
Improvement in Ground Water	Groundwater has increased to 4.14 MT.
Fisheries	The state is ranked 3rd in inland fishery resources and 8th in Fish production.

Source: *Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023*

Farmers are also encouraged to adopt Micro Irrigation techniques, such as drip irrigation or sprinkler systems, to make available water more efficient and convenient. As of November 2022, a total of 20.35 lakh acres of land have been covered under micro-irrigation practices (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Figure 7 - Trends in Gross Area Irrigated (by all sources) in Telangana

Source: Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Government of Telangana

Seeds & Fertilisers: High-quality seeds are grown in the state on account of the favourable climatic conditions that are present. Through cooperative societies, seeds and fertilisers are provided to farmers in advance at reduced rates at the village level. Numerous international corporations have established processing facilities and warehouses to store the seeds generated in the state. The Government intends to give 1.66 lakh quintals of green manure seed to farmers in the state in 2022–2023 with a subsidy of Rs. 71.46 crores. Fertiliser supplies have increased by 46% from 25.36 lakh tonnes to 37.06 lakh tonnes between 2014–15 and 2021–22. The state is active in manufacturing high-quality seeds and seed certification in addition to seed distribution (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Table 10: Seed Production in Telangana.

Year	Seed Production (in Quintals)
2018-19	4,44,833
2019-20	5,75,017
2020-21	4,65,284
2021-22	1,56,413
2022-23	5,25,000

Source: Seed Development Corporation, Government of Telangana

Figure 8 - Fertiliser Consumption from the year 2018-19 to 2021-22 (in lakh tones) in Telangana

Source: Department of Agriculture, Government of Telangana

The state produced 5.25 lakh quintals of seed for various crops during the current fiscal year 2022–2023. The other States of Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Karnataka, and Chhattisgarh also receive seeds produced in the state. With these

programs, the Government is supplying the produce from the state to several other States across the nation and is also assuring food security. Hence, in the nation, Telangana is currently known as the "Seed Bowl of India" (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Table 11: Crop-wise Seed Production in Telangana

Crop Name	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23
Paddy	3,36,424	4,40,549	3,68,490	90,482	3,61,672
Bengal gram	53,257	78,014	80,029	50,612	30,000
Groundnut	18,351	32,553	9,927	4,212	30,000
Soybean	21,000	14,166	75	1,672	14,434
Red gram	4,886	1,708	4,029	2,350	9,885
Others	10,915	8,026	2,734	7,085	79,009
Total	4,44,833	5,75,016	4,65,284	1,56,413	5,25,000

Source: State Seeds Development Corporation, Government of Telangana

Mechanisation - Lesser Drudgery: Farm mechanisation in agriculture plays a crucial role in boosting crop productivity, increasing production, reducing cultivation costs, and enabling the timely completion of farming operations. To expand cultivation and improve productivity per unit area, the introduction of mechanised implements like powered tractors, power tillers, and renewable energy sources is necessary. The Government is considering providing various farm machinery and implements to farmers on a subsidised basis, considering factors such as types of crops grown, soil conditions, local situations, and state requirements (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

The state aims to double farm mechanisation in the future to address the issue of labour shortage in farming. Additionally, the scheme also includes the distribution of animal-drawn implements, tractor-drawn implements, high-cost machinery, mini tractors, post-harvest equipment, and plant protection equipment to farmers on a subsidised basis. Since the formation of the state, a total of Rs. 963 crores have been spent on farm mechanisation, benefiting 6.66 lakh farmers with the provision of farm implements such as tractors, harvesters, and tarpaulins. To date, the Government has provided 19,607 tractors to farmers in the state on a subsidised basis (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Rythu Bandhu - Financial Aid for Farmers

The Government introduced the Rythu Bandhu Scheme in 2018, acknowledging the significance of financial aid for farmers to cover the basic costs of cultivation. Under this scheme, landowning farmers in the state receive Rs. 10,000/- per acre per year, which is higher compared to other states. For instance, in Andhra Pradesh, the assistance is Rs. 7,500 per farmer family per year. In Jharkhand, it is Rs. 5,000 per marginal and small farmer per acre per year, and in West Bengal, it is Rs. 10,000 per year for one acre or more of cultivable land (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Moreover, the Rythu Bandhu Scheme has been extended to all landowning farmers regardless of the size of their landholding. The Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations (ICRIER) has endorsed this direct investment support introduced by the Government of Telangana, stating that the Rythu Bandhu scheme is more beneficial than other alternative schemes due to its simplicity in implementation, transparency, and inclusivity, as mentioned in a brief note prepared by ICRIER.

Figure 9 - Status of Rythu Bandhu Scheme from Vanakalam 2018-19 to Vanakalam 2022-23

Source: Department of Agriculture, Govt. of India

Figure 10 - Status of Rythu Bandhu Scheme from Vanakalam 2018-19 to Vanakalam 2022-23

Source: Department of Agriculture, Govt. of Telangana

Reference for graphs: Vanakalam - Kharif Season, Yasangi - Rabi Season

Rythu Bima - Insurance for Farmers

The Government introduced a flagship group life insurance scheme called Rythu Bima in 2018, aimed at providing financial relief and social security to family members or dependents in case of the death of a farmer due to any reason. Under this scheme, if an enrolled farmer between the ages of 18 and 59 passes away, including due to natural causes, an insured amount of Rs 5 Lakhs will be deposited into the designated nominee's account within ten days. The entire premium for this insurance is borne by the state, without imposing any burden on the farmer, regardless of their land holding size.

One unique aspect of this scheme is that the nominee does not need to approach any office for claim settlement. Instead, the village-level outreach officer will collect information from the revenue department and submit it to the Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) on behalf of the nominee. The claimed amount will then be transferred directly to the nominee's account. Since its implementation in 2018, the Government has settled claims amounting to Rs. 4,771 crores and transferred the amount to 95,416 bereaved families for the period from 2018-19 to 2022-23. The entire process of enrolment, claim settlement, and disbursement is done online (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Figure 11 - Status of Rythu Bima in Telangana

Source: Department of Agriculture, Govt. of Telangana

Rythu Vedika - Agriculture Extension

The Government has launched an initiative to bring farmers together on a common platform called Rythu Vedika (RV), which is constructed in every Agriculture Extension Officer Cluster comprising 1-3 villages. Currently, there are a total of 2,601 RVs that have been built in the state. Each RV is constructed at the cost of Rs. 22 lakhs, with Rs. 12 lakhs being funded by the Agriculture Department and Rs. 10 lakhs from MGNREGA (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act) funds. The purpose of these RVs is to facilitate farmers in sharing information related to crops, markets, and other relevant topics that can help them achieve higher returns by cultivating profitable crops.

Additionally, Telangana Rythu Bhandu Samithi (TRBS) committees with a total membership of 1,60,990 individuals have been established at the village, Mandal, district, and state levels. These committees serve as a conduit between farmers and Agriculture & Allied Departments. Additionally, the Government started building multi-use cement "Kallams" (drying platforms) around the state for farmers to dry their agricultural harvest (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Structural Reforms

One of the weakest associations in the agriculture value chain is getting access to markets as well as obtaining information on which crops to be grown. With the increase in production, there are chances of supply-demand shocks which in turn result in less compensation for the farmers. Towards this issue, the Government has introduced multiple strategies in terms of pushing for crop diversification (through support for Oil Palm and other horticulture crops) and has given importance to allied sectors to diversify and gain more income for the farmers.

Crop Diversification: Crop diversification, as recommended by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), is considered an effective approach to relieving economic stress and promoting growth. It involves adding new crops or cropping systems to a farm, considering

the returns from value-added crops and marketing opportunities. The goal is to expand the crop portfolio of farmers to reduce dependence on a single crop for income generation.

The Government has emphasised the importance of crop diversification and recommended crops such as Groundnut, Sunflower, Sesame, Bengal gram, Black gram, Green gram, Jowar, Castor, Mustard, Safflower, and Palm oil. In the districts of Nirmal, Vikarabad, and Rangareddy, there was significant progress in crop diversification in the 2021-22 season, as measured by a crop diversification index, compared to Peddapalli, Karimnagar and Suryapet, which had the least diversified cropping patterns (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Palm Oil Cultivation: The Government has proposed a significant promotion of oil palm cultivation in the state to address the gap between the demand and supply of vegetable edible oils and reduce dependence on imports. Currently, there are 68,440 acres of oil palm cultivation, with 27,376 acres added after the formation of the state, resulting in a production of 2.6 lakh MTs of fresh fruit bunches (FFB).

However, the state produces only 52,666 MTs of crude palm oil, which falls short of the requirement of 3.66 lakh MTs. There are currently two processing units in the state with a capacity of 30 tonnes per hour each. The Government has, therefore, issued orders to allot Factory Zones for oil palm expansion in newly identified locations in the State (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Organic Farming: The Telangana government acknowledges the significance of organic farming, recognising the state's potential to excel in organic cultivation and serve as a model for others. It is argued that organic farming offers several advantages, such as producing high-quality food, preserving natural resources, protecting the environment, increasing income (despite potential yield fluctuations), and improving the overall well-being of farmers.

To support organic farming, the Telangana Organic Certification Authority (TOCA) provides organic certification to farmers and trade bodies in the state. The Telangana State Seed and Organic Certification Authority (TSSOCA) conducts inspections and certifications of agricultural products and food processing, ensuring compliance with National Programme for Organic Production (NPOP) standards and other international standards (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Despite the positive developments in organic farming, farmers in the state face challenges in selling their organic products in the market due to a lack of proper facilities. They struggle to find a separate platform for organic foods compared to conventional foods, making it difficult to market their cultivated organic products.

Agriculture Value Chain

While enhancing productivity is crucial for a thriving agricultural sector, it is equally important to focus on improving marketing connectivity, post-harvest handling, and processing to ensure that high-quality products reach the market. Efficient post-harvest management not only minimises losses but also enhances the value of agricultural products that are sold. The Government has undertaken various initiatives in this regard, which are elaborated on below.

Procurement: According to the Government, farmers' reliance on middlemen for the sale of their produce has decreased as a result of the State purchasing paddy from the farmers. This has given farmers more motivation to enhance their crop production. Over the past seven years, the Civil Supplies Department has acquired enormous amounts of paddy while guaranteeing the Minimum Support Price. Farmers have benefited from the procurement system during the last few years. The Government's purchases during these years of uncertainty have aided farmers in obtaining fair prices in the State (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Table 12: Procurement of Paddy and Cotton

Crop	Year	Quantity Purchased (LMTs)	No. of Farmers Benefited (lakhs)	Purchase Value (Crores)
Paddy	2019-20	111.26	19.74	20,384
	2020-21	141.07	21.63	26,609
	2021-22	120.61	22.43	23,605
Cotton	2019-20	21.62	9.15	11,749
	2020-21	17.89	5.49	10,167

Source: Department of Civil Supplies and Cotton Corporation of India

Milling and Warehouse Management: Since the establishment of the state, the Government has been actively engaged in developing the agricultural infrastructure in the region. This includes the establishment of 2,200 Rice Mills with a combined capacity of one crore tonnes of rice per year. Additionally, the Telangana State Warehousing Corporation was created by the Government to enhance the warehousing facilities across the state.

With the assistance of NABARD, the Agricultural Marketing Department has constructed 457 warehouses at 347 locations, resulting in a total of 1,167 warehouses with a storage capacity of 24.73 lakh MTs in the state. This was achieved with an investment of Rs. 1,024 crores, leading to an increase in storage capacity. The Government has further planned to provide additional facilities and create a favourable environment for rice millers in the State (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Figure 12 - Year-wise Storage Capacity of Foodgrains in Telangana

Source: RBI Handbook of statistics on Indian Economy 2021-22

Processing: The state has introduced the Telangana State Food Processing policy with the aim of establishing food processing units in response to the increasing food production in the region. The policy encompasses various sectors such as rice milling, pulses, oilseeds, fruits, flowers, vegetables, meat, chicken, fish, milk, and dairy products for setting up food processing units. Since 2017, this sector has witnessed a fixed capital investment of Rs. 2,376 crores from 2,140 enterprises, resulting in the creation of 29,841 job opportunities. The food processing policy offers attractive financial incentives, including rebates on power and water tariffs for units established in designated zones.

It also provides plug-and-play infrastructure and special support for farmer producer groups, self-help groups, and vulnerable sections of society. To explore trade and investment opportunities in agro-based food processing, the Government has signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Thai Government. Furthermore, it was reported that the Government is collaborating with the Government of India on the "Formalisation of Micro Food Processing Enterprises" initiative, which has an outlay of Rs. 10,000 Crore and will be implemented over a five-year period from 2021-25 (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

e-NAM: e-NAM was established with the goal of linking marketplaces in states all across the nation through a common online platform, hence promoting uniformity in agricultural selling. On e-NAM, around 175 commodities, including food grains, oil seeds, fruits, and vegetables, are exchanged. 57 Agricultural Market Committees (AMC) around the state are currently using e-NAM. The Prime Minister's Excellence Prize has been given to the AMC, Nizamabad, and Kesamudram for their outstanding e-NAM implementation. Weighing Integration and Payments under e-NAM are being introduced by the State (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Table 13: Achievements Under e- NAM

Achievements Under e- NAM (as of 31st Oct. 2022)	
Quantity Traded (Lakh MTs)	48.82
Volume (Crores)	16,469
Number of traders registered	5,788
Number of commission agents registered	4,727
Number of farmers registered	18,23,649

Source: Agriculture Marketing Department

Efforts of the Government in Strengthening Agriculture Statistics

As per the government report named "Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook of 2023", the state has taken various measures to strengthen agriculture statistics in order to improve the accuracy of area and yield estimations. These efforts include modernising the data collection process and introducing supportive supervisory practices to ensure error-free final data. Three key initiatives undertaken by the Government are:

- Activity Logger:** A mobile application that allows frontline personnel in the agriculture department to report their daily activities and quantify their efforts for each activity. The data generated from this application is used to monitor and measure the performance of 2,600 Agricultural Extension Officers (AEOs) working across the

state. This helps in identifying misalignment in resource allocation and making necessary adjustments.

- ii. **Remote Sensing-based Estimation:** The Government has initiated a pilot project for remote sensing-based area estimation for major crops like Paddy, Maize, Groundnut, Jowar, Green gram, Black gram, and Bengal gram during the Rabi Season (Yasangi) 2021-22. This pilot project is done in coordination with Satsure, a well-established remote sensing-based agency, and provides area estimates at the village level. The same pilot project was extended to Kharif (Vaanakalam) in 2022 for ten crops, including Paddy, Cotton, Maize, Groundnut, Jowar, Soya bean, Chilli, Turmeric, Green gram, and Red gram.
- iii. **Survey CTO Application:** The agriculture department uses a mobile-based data collection platform called Survey CTO Application for verification of area enumeration. This platform allows for complex skip patterns, geo-tracing, and tagging of crops, ensuring the collection of authentic data during agricultural area enumeration surveys. The use of this application provides another level of check with real-time data gathering to ensure the accuracy of recorded data. The state has implemented Survey CTO in identifying correction factors in the area enumeration work across the State since Vaanakalam, 2021, onwards. To improve the accuracy of the area and yield estimations, the Government has modernised the data collection process and introduced supportive supervisory practices to ensure error-free final data.

Allied Sectors - Animal Husbandry

To achieve the goal of doubling farmers' income, the Indian Government has recommended diversifying from farm income to non-farm income and improving livestock productivity. Animal Husbandry activities, such as sheep rearing and dairy farming, can augment farm income and provide additional employment opportunities for farmers. The State

government has prioritised this sector and implemented various schemes to support farmers engaged in animal husbandry activities.

Sheep Rearing and Development Programme (SRDP): The Government has launched the Sheep Rearing and Development Programme (SRDP) with the aim of strengthening the rural economy and ensuring sustainable livelihoods for the shepherd community in the state. Under this scheme, 21 sheep (20+1) are provided to beneficiaries with a subsidy component of 75% of the unit cost, amounting to Rs 1.25 lakhs. In the first phase of implementation, Rs 5,001 crores have been spent, and a total of 82.64 lakh sheep have been distributed to 3,93,552 members of Primary Sheep Breeder Cooperative Societies in the State.

The sheep population has increased from 1.28 crore to 1.91 crores, and meat production has increased from 5.42 lakh Metric Tonnes to 10.04 lakh Metric Tonnes between 2015-16 and 2021-22 in the state. The state ranks first in the Country with a contribution of 25.72% to the total sheep population, as per the 20th Livestock Census. In the second phase of implementation (2022-23 and 2023-24), the unit cost has been enhanced from Rs. 1,25,000 to Rs. 1,75,000, aiming to cover 3.50 lakh beneficiaries with a financial outlay of Rs. 6,085 crores in the State (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Table 14: % Contribution of Non-Special Category States to the Sheep Population in the Country.

States	% Contribution of Non Special Category States to the Sheep Population in the Country (2019-20)
Telangana	25.72
Andhra Pradesh	23.7
Karnataka	14.95
Rajasthan	10.64
Tamil Nadu	6.06
Maharashtra	3.64

Table 14 Continued

States	% Contribution of Non Special Category States to the Sheep Population in the Country (2019-20)
Gujarat	2.42
Odisha	1.75
Uttar Pradesh	1.35

Source: RBI Handbook of Statistics on Indian Economy 2021-22

Allied Sectors - Dairy

Dairy farming is an important means for farmers to increase their earnings and improve access to nutritious food for their families. To encourage farmers to take up dairy farming, the Government has introduced a scheme to provide Rs. 4/- per litre of milk collected as an incentive to members of Cooperative Dairies. The incentive amount is directly credited to their respective bank accounts every month. So far, 29.39 lakh beneficiaries have been enrolled in the scheme, and Rs. 361 crores have been spent on it. Milk production has increased by 38% (from 42 lakh tons in 2014-15 to 58 lakh tons in 2021-22), and milk procurement has increased from 1.17 lakh litres per day to 5.60 lakh litres per day (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Allied Sectors - Fodder Production and Development

With 141.31 lakh livestock units in the state, the availability of quality feed and fodder is essential for improving livestock production and productivity. To improve the accessibility of fodder, the Government has emphasised the supply of fodder seed to needy farmers with a subsidy of 75%. So far, 1,025 MTs of fodder seed have been supplied to needy farmers at the cost of Rs. 8.00 crores. In the current year 2022-23, it is expected that about 51,250 acres will be sown under fodder crops to produce about 15.00 lakh MTs of green fodder. The Government has planned to supply the required fodder seed to farmers during the year 2022-23 (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Allied Sectors - Poultry

In 2021-22, Telangana ranked third in egg production in the Country, with an annual output of 1,667 crore eggs, accounting for 12.98% of the total production. To encourage the poultry sector, the Government has been providing free power up to 200/unit to poultry farms since 2015 (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

Table 15: % Contribution of Non-Special Category States to National Egg Production in 2021-22.

States	% Contribution of Non-Special Category States to National Egg Production in 2021-22
Andhra Pradesh	20.45
Tamil Nadu	16.49
Telangana	12.98
West Bengal	8.6
Karnataka	6.24
Haryana	5.96
Maharashtra	5.25
Punjab	4.63
Uttar Pradesh	4.63

Source: RBI Handbook of statistics on Indian Economy 2021-22

Allied Sectors - Aquaculture

The fisheries sector is a rapidly growing industry in Telangana, providing high-income and employment opportunities. It plays a crucial role in the socio-economic development of fishermen's families by generating income and providing nutritional food to the population. Recognising the potential of this sector, the Government has implemented various initiatives, such as strengthening government seed hatcheries to enhance seed production, stocking water bodies with advanced fingerlings, and promoting new technologies.

Telangana stands out as the only state where all suitable water bodies are stocked with quality fish seed through 100% grants. Additionally, to create employment opportunities for women groups, customised vehicles for raw fish sales and Ready-to-Eat fish food are being provided in GHMC limits and districts with an outlay of Rs 15.00 crores. The Government has also launched the "Integrated Fisheries Development Scheme" with an outlay of Rs 1,000 crores in 2017-18, in collaboration with the National Cooperative Development Corporation (NCDC), for the welfare of the fisheries community (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023). As a result of these incentives and government support, fish and prawn production in the state has increased from 2.68 lakh tonnes (2.6 lakh tonnes of fish and 0.08 lakh tonnes of prawns) in 2014-15 to 3.90 lakh tonnes (3.76 lakh tonnes of fish and 0.14 lakh tonnes of prawns) in 2021-22. The value of production has also risen from Rs. 2,637 crores to Rs. 5,860 crores during the same period (Telangana Socio-Economic Outlook, 2023).

FUTURE CHALLENGES

While the Telangana government has introduced several initiatives to boost the agriculture and allied sector in the state, there are still a few hindrances and challenges that need to be addressed in the future. This section of the paper introduces such roadblocks and addresses them through various suggestions.

Overproduction of Paddy and Cotton

Relying too heavily on just two crops increases the risks associated with production and pricing and makes farmers vulnerable to devastation from pests, diseases, and environmental challenges (Reddy, 2022). This was evident in Telangana in 2022, when the chilli crop failed, resulting in significant financial losses for farmers (Shagun, 2022). Furthermore, in 2021, excess production of paddy led to conflicts between the Telangana government and the Central Government over procurement issues, with farmers facing distress sales below the Minimum Support Price (MSP) (Sharma, 2021).

Similarly, the cultivation of cotton in Telangana poses possible environmental challenges due to its high-water consumption, use of fertilisers and pesticides, and genetic modification (Dewan, 2019). To promote sustainable production, it is crucial to adopt better cotton standards that prioritise minimising the harmful impact of crop protection practices, efficient water usage, soil health, conservation of natural habitats, fibre quality preservation, and fair labour practices (World Wildlife Fund, n.d.).

To address the issue of over-reliance on a few crops, diversification of crops beyond paddy, such as pulses and oilseeds, should be encouraged in Telangana. Efforts are already being made in this direction to promote a more balanced and sustainable approach to agriculture.

Crop Diversification

As per the Telangana State Processing Society, the state has adopted a "one district-one product" approach to promote crop diversification. This involves encouraging farmers to switch to high-value crops by providing them with the necessary infrastructure, such as processing units and post-harvest facilities, specific to each commodity in each district. The Department of Agriculture is also promoting alternate crops through demonstrations, farm mechanisation, value addition, and other site-specific activities.

Several schemes are being implemented in Telangana to diversify crops, including palm oil, horticulture, bamboo, and agro-forestry. Cash and kind incentives are also provided to cultivate alternate crops like palm oil, although with limited success. Crop diversification is essential to reduce dependency on paddy and cotton. However, past policies promoting pulses, oilseeds, and other crops have not been stable enough to trigger a shift from paddy, as alternate crops can be riskier in terms of yields and prices, despite fetching higher prices in some years (Reddy, 2022). To promote alternate crops effectively in the future, it is suggested that the Government must implement price guarantees

through minimum support price (MSP) procurement and promote the adoption of yield-enhancing technologies. This would help overcome the challenges associated with market prices and low yields and encourage farmers to adopt diverse crops in the State (Reddy, 2022).

Extreme Weather Conditions and Climate Change

Climate change can impact crop growing conditions in different regions, either positively or negatively. Changes in temperature, rainfall, and frost-free days are resulting in longer growing seasons in most states, which can have both positive and negative effects on food production (Gowda et al., 2018). Some farmers may benefit from longer growing seasons by planting longer-maturing crops or more crop cycles, while others may face challenges such as increased irrigation needs in hotter and longer growing seasons. Additionally, air pollution, as per Nolte et al. (2018), such as ground-level ozone, can damage crops, plants, and forests, leading to reduced photosynthesis, slower growth, and higher susceptibility to diseases (EPA, 2022).

In India, hydro-meteorological calamities such as heavy rainfall and floods have already caused significant damage to cropped areas between 2015-16 and 2021-22, as reported by the Ministry of Agriculture in a recent session of parliament. Drought, resulting from inadequate and deficient rainfall, has also been equally devastating, causing damage to approximately 35 million hectares of the cropped area between 2016-17 and 2021-22, according to data obtained through the Right to Information (RTI) Act.

A 2021 study conducted in the drought-prone districts of Telangana state in India also assessed the vulnerability of households to climate change. The study found that 79 per cent of the households were extremely vulnerable, 11.20 per cent were moderately vulnerable, and 9.65 per cent were resilient, based on cluster analysis results (Nedumaran, et al. 2021).

Therefore, it is crucial for governments at all levels to formulate region-specific policies to address barriers and unlock the potential of agriculture in mitigating the impacts of climate change. Such policies should be tailored to the unique needs and conditions of each region to effectively tackle the challenges posed by climate change in agriculture.

Cultivation of Palm Oil

The Government in Telangana is strongly supporting the growth of palm oil production, citing its low risk of animal attacks and ability to withstand harsh weather conditions. In the 2021-22 period, the state produced 46,171 metric tons of crude palm oil, with most of the plantations located in four districts. However, the Government plans to expand palm oil farming beyond the target set by the union government, aiming to cover 27 out of 33 districts in the state, excluding six districts which are facing water scarcity and are considered urban areas. The overall goal is to increase the current land under palm oil cultivation by 22 times (Pandey, 2022b).

Despite the positive outlook, there are a few possible challenges in palm oil cultivation. Small and marginal farmers might find it unfeasible due to a lack of productivity in the initial four years, as these plants have long gestation periods and only bear fruits after four years. Another challenge is water requirement, with each oil palm tree needing 200 to 300 litres of water per day. This necessitates careful irrigation and optimal use of available water resources, mostly groundwater, which may not be accessible to all farmers.

Some experts express concerns about the economic viability of the ambitious expansion of palm oil cultivation in the state. They caution that the heavy subsidies and government support may not be sustainable in the long term, and the state's reliance on importing other crops may pose economic risks for farmers and the agriculture sector. Furthermore, the expansion of palm oil plantations may also impact water quality in freshwater streams that millions of people depend on,

according to research from the University of Minnesota and Stanford University (Dubos, 2016).

As a result, decisions made by the Government regarding palm oil cultivation have significant implications for farmers and the environment. While promoting palm oil cultivation can bring economic benefits, it can also have adverse effects on the environment, including water quality and sustainability. Policymakers, therefore, should carefully consider the potential impacts of their decisions, balancing economic benefits with environmental conservation. It is crucial to promote sustainable palm oil cultivation practices that minimise harm to nature and ensure fair compensation for farmers.

Expanding the Nutritious Food Basket

Crop diversification has the potential to enhance nutrition security by expanding access to a diverse range of foods that can provide essential nutrients through multiple channels. Firstly, it can increase the availability of different types of crops that are rich in essential nutrients like vitamins, minerals, and fibre, thus helping to combat micronutrient deficiencies such as iron-deficiency anaemia, which is a prevalent public health concern in the state. According to a report presented by the Centre in Parliament in response to a query on the effectiveness of the Anaemia Mukh Bharat (AMB) program in 2023, the percentage of anaemic children in the State of Telangana has risen from 60.7% in the National Family Health Survey-4 (NFHS-4) to 70% in NFHS-5. Crop diversification can potentially address the issue of limited dietary diversity, thereby improving nutrition outcomes (TNN, 2023). Secondly, providing a diverse food basket can enhance the availability of food throughout the year. By cultivating crops with different growing seasons, farmers can ensure a consistent supply of food, which can reduce food insecurity and malnutrition.

Thirdly, it can generate economic benefits for farmers, leading to improved nutrition security for themselves as well. By diversifying their

crops and their nutrition provision, farmers can reduce their reliance on a single crop, mitigating the risks associated with crop failure or price fluctuations. This can stabilise their income, increase their purchasing power, and improve their ability to access nutritious foods.

CONCLUSION

As we have argued in this paper, the agricultural sector in Telangana has undergone significant changes and improvements since the formation of the state. The Government of Telangana has taken proactive steps to prioritise agriculture as a key sector for economic growth and rural development. Since 2014-15, the gross value added of agriculture at constant prices has increased by 46.6 per cent and the annual average growth rate of the primary sector has been 15.8 which is above the Indian average. Also, the contribution of the primary sector to gross state value added at current prices has increased by 4.6 per cent from 2014-15 to 2020-21.

Through various initiatives, policies, and programs, the state has made significant strides in improving agricultural productivity, enhancing farmer welfare, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices. One of the major achievements of Telangana's agriculture sector has been the adoption of innovative technologies and modern farming practices.

The Government has promoted the use of advanced irrigation techniques, such as micro-irrigation systems and lift irrigation, which has resulted in efficient water utilisation and increased crop yields. Additionally, the state has encouraged the use of high-yielding crop varieties and modern agricultural machinery, contributing to higher productivity and income for farmers. Furthermore, the Government has implemented several farmer-centric initiatives aimed at improving their socio-economic well-being. These include providing financial support through loan waivers, crop insurance schemes, and direct cash transfers.

Despite the progress made, there are still challenges and hindrances that need to be addressed in the future. Along with securing adequate diverse nutrients for human health, one of the main challenges is climate change, with irregular rainfall patterns and increasing temperatures posing risks to agricultural productivity. Sustainable management of natural resources, including water and soil, remains a critical concern for ensuring the long-term viability of agriculture in the state. Access to credit, technology, and markets also needs to be improved to enable small and marginal farmers to participate effectively in the agricultural value chain.

In conclusion, Telangana has made remarkable strides in transforming its agriculture sector since its formation. The Government's proactive approach, innovative initiatives, and focus on farmer welfare have contributed to increased agricultural productivity, improved livelihoods, and sustainable agricultural practices. However, challenges remain, and continued efforts are needed to address them and ensure a resilient and sustainable agricultural sector in Telangana. It is imperative that policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders work collaboratively to overcome these challenges and pave the way for a prosperous future for Telangana's agriculture sector.

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